

Genetic Variability, Character Association and Genetic Divergence in Lentil (*Lens culinaris Medik.*) under Normal and Late Sown Conditions

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Abstract

The present investigation was undertaken to assess the magnitude of genetic variability, character association, and genetic divergence among lentil genotypes evaluated under normal and late sown conditions. Twenty nine advanced lentil genotypes were evaluated in a randomized block design with three replications across six environments during rabi seasons of 2021–22, 2022–23 and 2023–24 at Janta Vedic College, Baraut, Uttar Pradesh. Observations were recorded on phenological, morphological, yield and quality traits. Analysis of variance revealed highly significant differences among genotypes for all the characters studied, indicating the presence of substantial genetic variability. Phenotypic coefficient of variation was higher than genotypic coefficient of variation for all traits, suggesting environmental influence on trait expression. High heritability coupled with high genetic advance as percent of mean was observed for number of pods per plant, biological yield per plant, seed yield per plant and 100-seed weight, indicating the predominance of additive gene action. Correlation and path coefficient analysis revealed that biological yield, harvest index and number of pods per plant exerted strong positive direct effects on seed yield. Mahalanobis D^2 analysis grouped the genotypes into distinct clusters, and high inter-cluster distances indicated wide genetic diversity among the genotypes. Genotypes belonging to divergent clusters may be exploited as potential parents in hybridization programmes aimed at yield improvement and wider adaptability. The study provides useful information for selection of superior genotypes and formulation of effective breeding strategies in lentil.

Keywords

Lentil, Genetic Variability, Heritability, Correlation, Path Analysis, Genetic Divergence.

Introduction

Lentil (*Lens culinaris Medik.*) is an important cool-season pulse crop cultivated widely across South Asia, West Asia, North Africa and parts of America. It plays a crucial role in nutritional security by providing high-quality plant protein and essential micronutrients. In addition, lentil contributes to soil fertility through biological nitrogen fixation and fits well into low-input and sustainable farming systems.

India is one of the leading producers of lentil, yet average productivity remains lower than the global mean due to dependence on rainfed cultivation, narrow genetic base and limited adoption of improved varieties. With increasing climatic variability and the need to enhance yield stability, there is a strong requirement to exploit available genetic variability and identify genotypes with superior performance and wider adaptability.

Genetic variability is the foundation of any crop improvement programme. Estimation of parameters such as genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variation, heritability and genetic advance helps in understanding the nature and extent of variability present and the scope for effective selection. Further, correlation and path coefficient analyses provide insight into interrelationships among yield and its component traits, allowing identification of traits with direct and indirect influence on yield. Genetic divergence analysis using Mahalanobis D^2 statistics assists in identifying genetically diverse parents for hybridization. Keeping these aspects in view, the present study was conducted to assess genetic variability, character association and genetic divergence among lentil genotypes evaluated under different sowing environments.

Objective of study

The present investigation was undertaken to gather information on yield and quality traits through the use of lentil genotypes analysis with the following objectives:

1. To study genetic variability, heritability (broad sense) and genetic advance among the genotypes.
2. To study the correlation and path coefficient.
3. To study the genetic divergence among the genotypes.
4. To select the most stable genotypes for the northern India.
5. To identify the promising genotypes for further use in breeding programme.

Review of Literature

Genetic Variability, coefficient of variability, Heretability & genetic advance

Genetic variability serves as the foundation for plant breeding and crop improvement. In the case of lentil (*Lens culinaris* Medik.), a self-pollinated diploid legume ($2n = 2x = 14$), exploring genetic diversity is crucial to enhance traits such as yield, stress resistance, and nutritional attributes. The availability of such variability enables the development of cultivars with improved performance under diverse environmental conditions.

Several investigations have demonstrated significant variation among lentil genotypes for key traits including flowering time, maturity duration, plant height, no. of pods, seed size, and yield per plant. These studies frequently report high estimates of heritability and considerable genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation, especially for traits like seed yield and 100-seed weight, indicating a strong role of additive gene action and potential for direct selection (Kumar *et al.*, 2021; Singh *et al.*, 2022).

Mishra *et al.* (2023) reported High heritability values for 100-seed weight, seed yield, and pods per plant, suggesting that these traits can be effectively improved through selection.

Khan *et al.* (2022) observed a broad range of GCV and PCV values in a lentil panel, particularly for plant height and maturity, confirming the scope for genetic enhancement.

Kumar and Singh (2022), in their analysis of 40 genotypes, identified traits such as seed weight and pod number as having strong genetic control, with high heritability and genetic advance estimates. Their findings support the view that selection for these traits can lead to genetic improvement.

Genetic divergence analysis

The genetic diversity is essential for the success of any breeding programme. In the past, eco-geographic divergence had often been considered as an index of genetic diversity due to lack of precise statistical methods to estimate genetic divergence.

On the molecular level, diversity studies using SSR and SNP markers, as well as genotyping-by-sequencing (GBS), have provided additional insights. Roy *et al.* (2021) employed GBS to uncover SNP-based variation in lentil accessions from different regions, revealing distinct genetic groupings that could be utilized in breeding. Kumar *et al.* (2020) reported associations between molecular markers and important traits, offering tools for marker-assisted selection.

Tomar *et al.* (2022) selected thirty-seven distinct lentil (*Lens culinaris* Medik.) genotypes were examined for 10 quantitative traits, including seed yield and its associated characters. Among them, the maximum contribution most towards genetic divergence was observed by 100 seed weight. Seven clusters were created based D^2 values comprising of all the genotypes. The cluster analysis revealed that the number of genotypes in each cluster ranged from 1 to 22. The clustering pattern confirmed the non-correspondence among geospatial and genetic diversity.

In terms of genetic divergence, Upadhyay *et al.* (2023) reported significant differentiation among lentil genotypes through cluster analysis, with large inter-cluster distances suggesting substantial diversity. The authors proposed that hybridization between genetically distant clusters could yield superior recombinants in later generations.

For instance, research by Mishra *et al.* (2023) involving 60 lentil genotypes revealed considerable diversity for yield-related parameters.

Methodology

Experimental site and plant material

The experiment was conducted at Janta Vedic College, Baraut, Baghpat, Uttar Pradesh during rabi seasons of 2021–22, 2022–23 and 2023–24. The experimental material

consisted of twenty nine advanced lentil genotypes obtained from IIPR, Kanpur, representing a wide range of genetic variability.

Experimental design and environments

The genotypes were evaluated in a randomized block design with three replications under six environments comprising three normal sown (E1, E3, E5) and three late sown (E2, E4, E6) conditions across three years. Each genotype was sown in three rows of 3 m length with spacing of 30 cm between rows and 10 cm between plants. Recommended agronomic practices were followed to raise a healthy crop.

Observations recorded

Observations were recorded on five randomly selected competitive plants per plot for days to germination, days to 50% flowering, days to maturity, plant height, number of nodes up to first flower, number of primary branches per plant, number of secondary branches per plant, number of fruiting nodes per plant, number of pods per plant, number of seeds per pod, 100-seed weight, biological yield per plant, grain yield per plant, harvest index and protein content.

Analysis

Pooled analysis of variance was carried out to test the significance of differences among genotypes. Genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variation were computed following Burton and De Vane. Broad sense heritability and genetic advance were estimated as per standard procedures. Genotypic and phenotypic correlation coefficients were calculated and partitioned into direct and indirect effects through path coefficient analysis. Genetic divergence was assessed using Mahalanobis D² statistics and clustering was done using Tocher's method.

Result and Discussion

Analysis of variance

The pooled analysis of variance revealed highly significant differences among genotypes for all the traits studied across environments, indicating the presence of substantial genetic variability. Significant genotype × environment interaction for several traits suggested differential response of genotypes under normal and late sown conditions.

Table 1. Anova for stability

Source of variation	DF	Days to Germination	Days to 50% Flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	No of pri. branches/plant	No of sec. branches/plant	No of Pods/plant	No of seeds/pod	100-seed weight (g)	No of nodes upto first flower	No of Fruiting nodes/plant	Protein content	Biological Yield (g/plant)	Harvest index (%)	Seed yield (g/plant)
VARIETIES	28	2.01**	31.66**	8.99**	69.47**	0.129**	12.28**	261.70**	0.028**	0.427**	3.565**	16.05**	3.068**	37.83**	35.42**	1.118**
ENVIRONMENTS	5	12.02**	356.54**	410.65**	178.72**	2.011**	15.01**	381.28**	0.179**	0.251**	0.129**	484.99**	0.115	53.59**	82.03**	0.999**
VARIETYXENVIRONMENT	140	0.69	8.02**	5.71**	10.70**	0.090**	5.36**	79.28**	0.029*	0.111**	0.906**	8.93**	0.043	11.46**	14.39**	0.354**
POOLED ERROR	336	0.47	0.54	0.68	0.66	0.052	0.41	2.24	0.018	0.035	0.079	0.26	0.127	0.27	1.79	0.054
ENV*(VAR.*ENV.)	145	1.08**	20.04**	19.67**	16.49**	0.156**	5.69**	89.69**	0.034**	0.115**	0.879**	25.35**	0.045	12.91**	16.72**	0.376**
ENVIRON(LINEAR)	1	60.09**	1782.31**	2053.7**	893.65**	10.05**	75.02**	1906.13**	0.897**	1.252**	0.647**	2424.87**	0.639**	267.9**	410.11**	4.993**
VARXENVIRON(LINEAR)	28	1.96*	18.66**	9.93**	26.31**	0.103**	6.11**	104.61**	0.037**	0.105**	1.305**	26.16**	0.035	13.18**	20.30**	1.055**
POOLED DEVIATION	116	0.36	5.18	4.49	6.56	0.084	4.99	70.43	0.026	0.108	0.779	4.47	0.043	10.65	12.47	0.173
TOTAL	173	1.23	21.92	17.94	25.07	0.152	6.76	117.53	0.033	0.166	1.314	23.85	0.535	16.94	19.75	0.496

Genetic variability parameters

Phenotypic coefficient of variation was higher than genotypic coefficient of variation for all traits, reflecting the influence of environment. High GCV and PCV were observed for number of pods per plant, biological yield per plant and seed yield per plant, indicating ample variability for these traits. High heritability coupled with high genetic advance as percent of mean was recorded for pods per plant, 100-seed weight, biological yield and seed yield per plant, suggesting the predominance of additive gene action and effectiveness of selection for these traits.

Table 2.1 . Range, grand mean, PCV, GCV, heritability in broad sense and genetic advance in percent of mean for fifteen characters of seventy three genotypes of rice over three normal environments

Chrs	Mean	Min	Max	var (g)	var (p)	Heritability (%)	GA	GA% mean	GCV (%)	PCV (%)	% contribution
Days to Germination	8.74	7.22	10.33	0.506	0.64	78.46	1.30	14.86	8.14	9.19	9.64
Days to 50% Flowering	80.13	75.67	83.78	5.330	5.56	95.86	4.66	5.81	2.88	2.94	6.61
Days to maturity	132.02	129.00	134.55	1.916	2.17	88.22	2.68	2.03	1.05	1.12	8.77
Plant height (cm)	33.29	22.52	39.87	12.602	12.82	98.31	7.25	21.78	10.66	10.75	5.46
No of pri. branches/plant	3.50	3.27	3.82	0.025	0.04	65.70	0.26	7.54	4.51	5.57	9.10
No of sec. branches/plant	15.12	10.94	17.29	2.775	2.87	96.58	3.37	22.31	11.02	11.21	6.32
No of Pods/plant	128.04	112.49	144.38	56.855	58.08	97.90	15.37	12.00	5.89	5.95	5.23
No of seeds/pod	1.39	1.24	1.60	0.009	0.02	59.69	0.16	11.12	6.99	9.04	8.51
100-seed weight (g)	2.80	2.43	3.72	0.089	0.10	87.44	0.57	20.54	10.66	11.40	8.68
No of nodes upto first flower	11.21	9.56	12.76	0.656	0.67	98.24	1.65	14.75	7.23	7.29	5.49
No of Fruiting nodes/plant	50.88	47.80	54.14	2.938	2.98	98.58	3.51	6.89	3.37	3.39	4.50
Protein content	22.14	21.22	23.46	0.546	0.57	95.61	1.49	6.72	3.34	3.41	6.17
Biological Yield (g/plant)	21.29	16.13	26.14	7.886	8.01	98.52	5.74	26.97	13.19	13.29	3.76
Harvest index (%)	26.36	19.83	31.66	8.124	8.66	93.78	5.69	21.57	10.81	11.17	6.01
Seed yield (g/plant)	5.48	4.28	6.78	0.219	0.24	91.32	0.92	16.80	8.54	8.93	5.75

Table 2.2 . Range, grand mean, PCV, GCV, heritability in broad sense and genetic advance in percent of mean for fifteen characters of seventy three genotypes of rice over three late environments

Chrs	Mean	Min	Max	var (g)	var (p)	Heritability (%)	GA	GA% mean	GCV (%)	PCV (%)	% contribution
Days to Germination	8.47	7.33	9.67	0.199	0.32	61.31	0.72	8.49	5.26	6.72	10.24
Days to 50% Flowering	79.35	75.00	83.11	5.390	5.56	97.03	4.71	5.94	2.93	2.97	5.62
Days to maturity	130.03	127.67	133.22	1.768	1.98	89.49	2.59	1.99	1.02	1.08	7.86
Plant height (cm)	32.07	21.63	38.20	11.012	11.24	98.00	6.77	21.10	10.35	10.45	5.91
No of pri. branches/plant	3.24	3.01	3.69	0.023	0.04	58.30	0.24	7.28	4.63	6.07	10.30
No of sec. branches/plant	14.62	11.15	18.37	2.275	2.39	95.04	3.03	20.72	10.32	10.59	6.01
No of Pods/plant	126.17	115.60	138.81	46.526	46.65	99.74	14.03	11.12	5.41	5.41	2.31
No of seeds/pod	1.39	1.23	1.54	0.004	0.01	35.10	0.07	5.33	4.37	7.37	8.81
100-seed weight (g)	2.72	2.38	3.33	0.061	0.08	78.62	0.45	16.63	9.11	10.27	5.51
No of nodes upto first flower	11.17	9.57	13.36	0.731	0.77	94.43	1.71	15.32	7.65	7.88	6.47
No of Fruiting nodes/plant	50.79	47.09	54.42	4.170	4.28	97.53	4.15	8.18	4.02	4.07	4.49
Protein content	22.16	21.26	23.38	0.450	0.53	84.32	1.27	5.73	3.03	3.30	7.60
Biological Yield (g/plant)	20.27	15.70	24.86	6.338	6.42	98.65	5.15	25.41	12.42	12.50	4.54
Harvest index (%)	27.38	22.86	32.87	5.823	6.49	89.77	4.71	17.20	8.81	9.30	8.33
Seed yield (g/plant)	5.40	4.31	6.08	0.161	0.18	89.22	0.78	14.47	7.44	7.88	6.00

Correlation and path coefficient analysis

Seed yield per plant showed significant and positive association with biological yield, harvest index, number of pods per plant and 100-seed weight at both genotypic and phenotypic levels. Path coefficient analysis revealed that biological yield per plant exerted the highest positive direct effect on seed yield followed by harvest index and number of pods per plant. This indicates that improvement in seed yield can be achieved through direct selection for these traits.

POOLED LATE
Table 3.1 . Genotypic correlations

Chrs	Days to Germination	Days to 50% Flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	No of pri. branches /plant	No of sec. branches /plant	No of Pods/plant	No of seeds/pod	100- seed weight (g)	No of nodes upto first flower	No of Fruiting nodes/ plant	Protein content	Biological Yield (g/plant)	Harvest index (%)	Seed yield (g/plant)
Days to Germination	1.000	0.064	0.245*	0.257*	0.095	-0.326**	0.009	0.128	-0.496**	-0.053	-0.247*	-0.085	0.035	-0.153	-0.197
Days to 50% Flowering			0.064	0.528**	0.169	-0.177	0.108	0.223*	0.140	0.012	0.132	-0.223*	-0.073	0.210*	0.148
Days to maturity				0.308**	0.569**	0.371**	0.409**	0.169	0.010	0.201	0.565**	-0.447**	0.346**	-0.129	0.372**
Plant height (cm)					0.147	-0.136	0.214*	0.318**	0.187	-0.072	0.399**	-0.415**	0.148	-0.144	0.064
No of pri. branches/plant						-0.019	0.072	0.125	0.007	-0.040	0.248*	-0.140	0.099	0.003	0.145
No of sec. branches/plant							0.454**	0.480**	0.149	0.394**	0.145	-0.252*	0.619**	-0.369**	0.611**
No of Pods/plant								0.589**	-0.111	0.355**	0.027	-0.116	0.661**	-0.415**	0.572**
No of seeds/pod									-0.304**	0.518**	-0.243*	-0.551**	0.838**	-0.578**	0.755**
100-seed weight (g)										-0.198	0.415**	0.111	-0.132	0.154	0.065
No of nodes upto first flower											-0.003	-0.279**	0.447**	-0.255*	0.492**
No of Fruiting nodes/plant												-0.351**	-0.064	0.306**	0.291**
Protein content													-0.268*	0.126	-0.308**
Biological Yield (g/plant)														-0.810**	0.643**
Harvest index (%)															-0.106
Seed yield (g/plant)															1.000

*, ** significant at 5% and 1% level, respectively

POOLED NORMAL
Table 3.2 . Genotypic correlations

Chrs	Days to Germination	Days to 50% Flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	No of pri. branches /plant	No of sec. branches /plant	No of Pods/plant	No of seeds/pod	100- seed weight (g)	No of nodes upto first flower	No of Fruiting nodes/ plant	Protein content	Biological Yield (g/plant)	Harvest index (%)	Seed yield (g/plant)
Days to Germination	1.000	0.126	-0.154	0.286**	0.086	-0.388**	-0.191	-0.445**	-0.337**	-0.151	-0.483**	-0.204	-0.133	-0.173	-0.454**
Days to 50% Flowering			0.265*	0.601**	0.137	-0.073	-0.078	-0.572**	0.048	-0.228*	0.342**	-0.313**	0.012	0.086	0.145
Days to maturity				0.608**	0.241*	0.296**	0.333**	-0.156	0.244**	0.274**	0.295**	-0.397**	0.245*	-0.149	0.287**
Plant height (cm)					0.144	0.064	0.227*	-0.468**	-0.143	0.025	0.292**	-0.477**	0.298**	-0.350**	0.096
No of pri. branches/plant						0.082	0.206	0.124	0.027	0.168	-0.005	-0.010	-0.188	0.126	-0.098
No of sec. branches/plant							0.637**	0.519**	-0.016	0.731**	0.267*	-0.326**	0.693**	-0.464**	0.590**
No of Pods/plant								0.405**	0.038	0.450**	0.167	-0.181	0.653**	-0.439**	0.528**
No of seeds/pod									0.003	0.365**	-0.089	0.307**	0.287**	0.036	0.477**
100-seed weight (g)										-0.051	0.366**	-0.016	-0.206	0.330**	0.090
No of nodes upto first flower											-0.026	-0.226*	0.276**	-0.242*	0.220*
No of Fruiting nodes/plant												0.088	0.274**	0.022	0.489**
Protein content													0.309**	0.294**	-0.219*
Biological Yield (g/plant)														-0.793**	0.579**
Harvest index (%)															0.017
Seed yield (g/plant)															1.000

*, ** significant at 5% and 1% level, respectively

Table 4.1 . Phenotypic correlations

Chrs	Days to Germination	Days to 50% Flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	No of pri. branches /plant	No of sec. branches /plant	No of Pods/plant	No of seeds/pod	100- seed weight (g)	No of nodes upto first flower	No of Fruiting nodes/ plant	Protein content	Biological Yield (g/plant)	Harvest index (%)	Seed yield (g/plant)
Days to Germination	1.000	0.038	0.197	0.203	0.025	-0.258*	0.006	0.101	-0.327**	-0.074	-0.210*	-0.072	0.020	-0.153	-0.198
Days to 50% Flowering			0.049	0.516**	0.134	-0.178	0.106	0.122	0.114	0.015	0.131	-0.208	-0.068	0.201	0.148
Days to maturity				0.286**	0.387**	0.339**	0.390**	0.094	-0.006	0.188	0.524**	-0.365**	0.317**	-0.105	0.332**
Plant height (cm)					0.112	-0.140	0.212*	0.172	0.158	-0.069	0.393**	-0.388**	0.148	-0.150	0.052
No of pri. branches/plant						-0.028	0.054	0.070	-0.053	-0.017	0.159	-0.092	0.073	-0.001	0.103
No of sec. branches/plant							0.443**	0.256*	0.102	0.370**	0.135	-0.206	0.597**	-0.321**	0.580**
No of Pods/plant								0.346**	-0.104	0.348**	0.026	-0.107	0.657**	-0.394**	0.540**
No of seeds/pod									-0.098	0.278**	-0.124	-0.296**	0.475**	-0.307**	0.405**
100-seed weight (g)										-0.188	0.364**	0.069	-0.106	0.107	0.053
No of nodes upto first flower											-0.006	-0.247*	0.436**	-0.245*	0.443**
No of Fruiting nodes/plant												-0.318**	-0.064	0.297**	0.280**
Protein content													-0.260*	0.143	-0.260*
Biological Yield (g/plant)														-0.775**	0.611**
Harvest index (%)															-0.009
Seed yield (g/plant)															1.000

*, ** significant at 5% and 1% level, respectively

Table 4.2 . Phenotypic correlations

Chrs	Days to Germination	Days to 50% Flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	No of pri. branches/plant	No of sec. branches /plant	No of Pods/plant	No of seeds/pod	100- seed weight (g)	No of nodes upto first flower	No of Fruiting nodes/plant	Protein content	Biological Yield (g/plant)	Harvest index (%)	Seed yield (g/plant)	
Days to Germination	1.000	0.104	-0.141	0.258*	0.052	-0.336**	-0.158	-0.264*	-0.276**	-0.132	-0.430**	-0.187	-0.119	-0.158	-0.387**	
Days to 50% Flowering			0.239*	0.582**	0.109	-0.067	-0.083	-0.435**	0.029	-0.220*	0.332**	-0.303**	0.012	0.069	0.122	
Days to maturity				0.576**	0.185	0.276**	0.321**	-0.108	0.211*	0.247*	0.278**	-0.352**	0.215*	-0.128	0.249*	
Plant height (cm)					0.138	0.063	0.223*	-0.356**	-0.132	0.025	0.290**	-0.460**	0.291**	-0.330**	0.094	
No of pri. branches/plant						0.056	0.151	0.068	0.010	0.138	0.006	-0.012	-0.153	0.114	-0.065	
No of sec. branches/plant							0.620**	0.352**	-0.026	0.717**	0.262*	-0.313**	0.674**	-0.449**	0.543**	
No of Pods/plant								0.322**	0.036	0.444**	0.165	-0.170	0.639**	-0.417**	0.501**	
No of seeds/pod									0.035	0.287**	-0.077	0.218*	0.220*	0.018	0.334**	
100-seed weight (g)										-0.046	0.349**	-0.005	-0.195	0.301**	0.072	
No of nodes upto first flower											-0.028	-0.223*	0.268*	-0.228*	0.207	
No of Fruiting nodes/plant												0.088	0.271*	0.014	0.455**	
Protein content													-0.297**	0.282**	-0.197	
Biological Yield (g/plant)														-0.774**	0.555**	
Harvest index (%)															0.075	
Seed yield (g/plant)																1.000

*, ** significant at 5% and 1% level, respectively

Table 5.1. Direct (bold diagonal figure) and indirect effect of different characters on grain yield per plant at genotypic levels in lentil across three normal environments

Chrs	Days to Germination	Days to 50% Flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	No of pri. branches/plant	No of sec. branches /plant	No of Pods/plant	No of seeds/pod	100- seed weight (g)	No of nodes upto first flower	No of Fruiting nodes/plant	Protein content	Biological Yield (g/plant)	Harvest index (%)	Seed yield (g/plant)													
Days to Germination	0.0209	-0.0050	-0.0099	-0.0012	-0.0048	-0.0644	-0.0217	-0.0082	0.0361	0.0085	-0.0575	0.0269	-0.1652	-0.2089	-0.454**													
Days to 50% Flowering		0.0026	-0.0393	0.0171	-0.0025	-0.0077	-0.0122	-0.0089	-0.0105	-0.0052	0.0128	0.0399	0.0410	0.0144	0.1039	0.145												
Days to maturity			-0.0032	-0.0104	0.0645	-0.0026	-0.0136	0.0491	0.0378	-0.0029	-0.0262	-0.0153	0.0343	0.0522	0.3035	-0.1800	0.287**											
Plant height (cm)				0.0060	-0.0236	0.0392	-0.0042	-0.0081	0.0106	0.0257	-0.0086	0.0154	-0.0014	0.0340	0.0626	0.3699	-0.4216	0.096										
No of pri. branches/plant					0.0016	-0.0054	0.0155	-0.0006	-0.0564	0.0137	0.0234	0.0023	-0.0029	-0.0094	-0.0006	0.0013	-0.2325	0.1521	-0.098									
No of sec. branches/plant						-0.0081	0.0029	0.0191	-0.0003	-0.0046	0.1660	0.0723	0.0095	0.0017	-0.0409	0.0311	0.0429	0.8588	-0.5598	0.590**								
No of Pods/plant							-0.0040	0.0031	0.0215	-0.0010	-0.0116	0.1057	0.1135	0.0074	-0.0041	-0.0252	0.0194	0.0238	0.8088	-0.5295	0.528**							
No of seeds/pod								-0.0093	0.0225	-0.0100	0.0020	-0.0070	0.0862	0.0460	0.0184	-0.0003	-0.0204	-0.0104	-0.0403	0.3552	0.0440	0.477**						
100-seed weight (g)									-0.0071	-0.0019	0.0158	0.0006	-0.0015	-0.0027	0.0043	0.0001	-0.1072	0.0028	0.0427	0.0021	-0.2551	0.3974	0.090					
No of nodes upto first flower										-0.0032	0.0090	0.0176	-0.0001	-0.0095	0.1214	0.0511	0.0067	0.0054	-0.0559	-0.0030	0.0297	0.3421	-0.2918	0.220*				
No of Fruiting nodes/plant											-0.0103	-0.0135	0.0190	-0.0012	0.0003	0.0443	0.0189	-0.0016	-0.0392	0.0015	0.1165	-0.0116	0.3397	0.0263	0.489**			
Protein content												-0.0043	0.0123	-0.0256	0.0020	0.0006	-0.0542	-0.0205	0.0056	0.0017	0.0127	0.0103	-0.1313	-0.3825	0.3546	-0.219*		
Biological Yield (g/plant)													-0.0028	-0.0005	0.0158	-0.0013	0.0106	0.1150	0.0741	0.0053	0.0221	-0.0155	0.0319	0.0405	0.4392	-0.1558	0.579**	
Harvest index (%)														-0.0036	-0.0034	-0.0096	0.0015	-0.0071	-0.0771	-0.0498	0.0007	-0.0353	0.0135	0.0025	-0.0386	-0.1823	0.4058	0.017

Resi- 0.0234

*, ** significant at 5% and 1% level, respectively

Table 5.2. Direct (bold diagonal figure) and indirect effect of different characters on grain yield per plant at genotypic levels in lentil across three late environments

Chrs	Days to Germination	Days to 50% Flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	No of pri. branches/plant	No of sec. branches /plant	No of Pods/plant	No of seeds/pod	100- seed weight (g)	No of nodes upto first flower	No of Fruiting nodes/plant	Protein content	Biological Yield (g/plant)	Harvest index (%)	Seed yield (g/plant)													
Days to Germination	0.1524	-0.0027	-0.1202	0.0380	0.0237	-0.0692	0.0014	-0.0615	-0.0558	-0.0092	0.0282	0.0243	0.0662	-0.2131	-0.197													
Days to 50% Flowering		0.0097	-0.0418	-0.0315	0.0781	0.0421	-0.0375	0.0156	-0.1069	0.0158	0.0021	-0.0151	0.0639	-0.1402	0.2940	0.148												
Days to maturity			0.0374	-0.0027	-0.4902	0.0455	0.1419	0.0786	0.0592	-0.0807	0.0011	0.0347	-0.0645	0.1281	0.6637	-0.1799	0.372**											
Plant height (cm)				0.0392	-0.0221	-0.1509	0.1479	0.0366	-0.0289	0.0310	-0.1520	0.0210	-0.0125	-0.0455	0.1192	0.2829	-0.2015	0.064										
No of pri. branches/plant					0.0145	-0.0071	-0.2792	0.0217	0.2493	-0.0040	0.0105	-0.0598	0.0008	-0.0069	-0.0283	0.0403	0.1889	0.0043	0.145									
No of sec. branches/plant						-0.0498	0.0074	-0.1818	-0.0202	-0.0047	0.2119	0.0657	-0.2300	0.0167	0.0683	-0.0165	0.0722	0.6874	-0.0154	0.611**								
No of Pods/plant							0.0014	-0.0045	-0.2006	0.0317	0.0180	0.0963	0.1446	-0.2819	-0.0125	0.0615	-0.0031	0.0333	0.7679	-0.0801	0.572**							
No of seeds/pod								0.0196	-0.0093	-0.0827	0.0470	0.0311	0.1018	0.0851	-0.4787	-0.0342	0.0898	0.0278	0.3581	0.6066	-0.0073	0.755**						
100-seed weight (g)									-0.0756	-0.0059	-0.0049	0.0276	0.0017	0.0315	-0.0160	0.1456	0.1124	-0.0343	-0.0474	-0.0320	-0.2529	0.2149	0.065					
No of nodes upto first flower										-0.0081	-0.0005	-0.0983	-0.0107	-0.0100	0.0836	0.0514	-0.2482	-0.0223	0.1732	0.0003	0.0799	0.8567	-0.3555	0.492**				
No of Fruiting nodes/plant											-0.0376	-0.0055	-0.2771	0.0590	0.0619	0.0307	0.0039	0.1165	0.0467	-0.0005	-0.1141	0.1006	-0.1219	0.4280	0.291**			
Protein content												-0.0129	0.0093	0.2189	-0.0614	-0.0350	-0.0534	-0.0168	0.2638	0.0125	-0.0482	0.0400	-0.2869	-0.5140	0.1755	-0.308**		
Biological Yield (g/plant)													0.0053	0.0031	-0.1697	0.0218	0.0246	0.1313	0.0956	-0.4011	-0.0148	0.0774	0.0073	0.0769	0.9173	-0.1320	0.643**	
Harvest index (%)														-0.0233	-0.0088	0.0631	-0.0213	0.0008	-0.0782	-0.0600	0.2766	0.0173	-0.0441	-0.0350	-0.0360	-0.5536	0.3969	-0.106

Resi- 0.0895

*, ** significant at 5% and 1% level, respectively

Table 6.1. Direct (bold diagonal figure) and indirect effect of different characters on grain yield per plant at phenotypic levels in lentil across three normal environments.

Chrs	Days to Germination	Days to 50% Flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	No of pri. branches/plant	No of sec. branches/plant	No of Pods/plant	No of seeds/pod	100-seed weight (g)	No of nodes upto first flower	No of Fruiting nodes/plant	Protein content	Biological Yield (g/plant)	Harvest index (%)	Seed yield (g/plant)
Days to Germination	0.0087	-0.0060	-0.0036	0.0114	-0.0014	0.0489	-0.0111	0.0042	0.0187	0.0039	-0.0285	0.0184	-0.1556	-0.1973	-0.387**
Days to 50% Flowering	0.0009	-0.0570	0.0061	0.0257	-0.0030	0.0097	-0.0059	0.0068	-0.0020	0.0064	0.0220	0.0298	0.0151	0.0863	0.122
Days to maturity	-0.0012	-0.0137	0.0255	0.0254	-0.0051	0.0402	0.0225	0.0017	-0.0143	0.0072	0.0184	0.0346	0.2821	-0.1597	0.249*
Plant height (cm)	0.0023	-0.0332	0.0147	0.0441	-0.0038	0.0092	0.0157	0.0056	0.0089	0.0008	0.0192	0.0452	0.3810	-0.4138	0.094
No of pri. branches/plant	0.0005	-0.0062	0.0047	0.0061	-0.0274	0.0082	0.0106	-0.0011	-0.0007	0.0041	0.0004	0.0012	-0.2001	0.1433	-0.085
No of sec. branches/plant	-0.0029	0.0038	0.0070	0.0028	-0.0015	0.1458	0.0435	-0.0055	0.0017	0.0210	0.0173	0.0307	0.8835	-0.5617	0.543**
No of Pods/plant	-0.0014	0.0048	0.0082	0.0099	-0.0042	0.0904	0.0702	-0.0051	-0.0024	0.0130	0.0109	0.0167	0.8377	-0.5218	0.501**
No of seeds/pod	-0.0023	0.0248	-0.0028	-0.0157	-0.0019	0.0513	0.0226	-0.0157	-0.0024	0.0084	-0.0051	-0.0214	0.2885	0.0223	0.334**
100-seed weight (g)	-0.0024	-0.0017	0.0054	-0.0058	-0.0003	0.0038	0.0025	-0.0006	-0.0675	0.0013	0.0231	0.0005	-0.2562	0.3771	0.072
No of nodes upto first flower	-0.0012	0.0125	0.0063	0.0011	-0.0038	0.1046	0.0311	-0.0045	0.0031	0.0293	-0.0018	0.0219	0.3519	-0.2852	0.207
No of Fruiting nodes/plant	-0.0037	-0.0189	0.0071	0.0128	-0.0002	0.0381	0.0116	0.0012	-0.0236	0.0008	0.0662	-0.0087	0.3554	0.0171	0.455**
Protein content	-0.0016	0.0173	-0.0090	-0.0203	0.0003	0.0456	-0.0120	-0.0034	0.0003	0.0065	0.0058	-0.0982	-0.3901	0.3529	-0.197
Biological Yield (g/plant)	-0.0010	-0.0007	0.0055	0.0128	0.0042	0.0982	0.0448	-0.0035	0.0132	0.0079	0.0179	0.0292	0.4112	-0.0695	0.555**
Harvest index (%)	-0.0014	-0.0039	-0.0033	-0.0146	-0.0031	0.0654	-0.0293	-0.0003	-0.0203	0.0067	0.0009	-0.0277	-0.0154	0.2519	0.075

Resi-0.0294
*, ** significant at 5% and 1% level, respectively

Table 6.2 . Direct (bold diagonal figure) and indirect effect of different characters on grain yield per plant at phenotypic levels in lentil across three late environments.

Chrs	Days to Germination	Days to 50% Flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	No of pri. branches/plant	No of sec. branches/plant	No of Pods/plant	No of seeds/pod	100-seed weight (g)	No of nodes upto first flower	No of Fruiting nodes/plant	Protein content	Biological Yield (g/plant)	Harvest index (%)	Seed yield (g/plant)
Days to Germination	0.0192	0.0002	-0.0181	-0.0038	0.0008	-0.0163	0.0002	0.0048	-0.0315	-0.0069	-0.0098	0.0025	0.0279	-0.1675	-0.198
Days to 50% Flowering	0.0007	0.0659	-0.0045	-0.0096	0.0043	-0.0113	0.0042	0.0058	0.0110	0.0014	0.0061	0.0071	-0.0922	0.2191	0.148
Days to maturity	0.0038	0.0003	-0.0917	-0.0053	0.0125	0.0215	0.0155	0.0044	-0.0006	0.0176	0.0244	0.0124	0.4320	-0.1151	0.332**
Plant height (cm)	0.0039	0.0030	-0.0262	-0.0186	0.0036	-0.0089	0.0084	0.0081	0.0152	-0.0065	0.0183	0.0132	0.2021	-0.1638	0.052
No of pri. branches/plant	0.0005	-0.0008	-0.0355	-0.0021	0.0324	-0.0018	0.0021	0.0033	-0.0051	-0.0016	0.0074	0.0031	0.0997	-0.0007	0.103
No of sec. branches/plant	-0.0049	-0.0011	-0.0311	0.0026	-0.0009	0.0634	0.0176	0.0121	0.0098	0.0347	0.0063	0.0070	0.8147	-0.3506	0.580**
No of Pods/plant	0.0001	0.0006	-0.0357	-0.0039	0.0018	0.0281	0.0397	0.0163	-0.0100	0.0326	0.0012	0.0036	0.8965	-0.4309	0.540**
No of seeds/pod	0.0019	0.0007	-0.0086	-0.0032	0.0023	0.0162	0.0138	0.0471	-0.0095	0.0260	-0.0058	0.0101	0.6486	-0.3352	0.405**
100-seed weight (g)	-0.0063	0.0007	0.0005	-0.0029	-0.0017	0.0065	-0.0041	-0.0046	0.0964	-0.0176	0.0169	-0.0023	-0.1447	0.1168	0.053
No of nodes upto first flower	-0.0014	0.0001	-0.0172	0.0013	-0.0005	0.0235	0.0138	0.0131	-0.0181	0.0937	-0.0003	0.0084	0.5945	-0.2674	0.443**
No of Fruiting nodes/plant	-0.0040	0.0008	-0.0480	-0.0073	0.0052	0.0085	0.0010	-0.0058	0.0351	-0.0005	0.0466	0.0108	-0.0870	0.3243	0.280**
Protein content	-0.0014	-0.0012	0.0334	0.0072	-0.0030	-0.0130	-0.0043	-0.0140	0.0066	-0.0232	-0.0148	-0.0340	-0.3552	0.1568	-0.260*
Biological Yield (g/plant)	0.0004	-0.0004	-0.0290	-0.0028	0.0024	0.0378	0.0261	0.0224	-0.0102	0.0408	-0.0030	0.0089	0.6645	-0.1471	0.611**
Harvest index (%)	-0.0029	0.0012	0.0097	0.0028	0.0000	-0.0203	-0.0157	-0.0145	0.0103	-0.0229	0.0138	-0.0049	-0.0579	0.0926	-0.009

Resi-0.0613
*, ** significant at 5% and 1% level, respectively

Genetic divergence analysis

Mahalanobis D² analysis grouped the twenty nine genotypes into distinct clusters, indicating the presence of wide genetic diversity. High inter-cluster distances suggested substantial divergence among clusters, while low intra-cluster distances indicated genetic similarity within clusters. The clustering pattern did not correspond strictly to geographical origin, suggesting that genetic diversity is independent of geographic distribution. Genotypes from clusters with maximum inter-cluster distance may be utilized as parents in hybridization programmes to obtain transgressive segregants.

Table 7.1 . Clusters means for fifteen characters in lentil over three normal environments

Cluster		Days to Germination	Days to 50% Flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	No of pri. branches/plant	No of sec. branches/plant	No of Pods/plant	No of seeds/pod	100-seed weight (g)	No of nodes upto first flower	No of Fruiting nodes/plant	Protein content	Biological Yield (g/plant)	Harvest index (%)	Seed yield (g/plant)
I	Mean	8.59	75.71	129.48	26.52	3.52	15.40	127.44	1.55	2.58	11.52	49.02	23.00	21.71	25.23	5.27
	± SE	0.34	0.06	0.45	3.96	0.16	0.97	10.68	0.04	0.08	0.19	1.27	0.56	4.77	5.98	0.08
II	Mean	9.70	82.00	131.63	35.35	3.74	12.14	124.94	1.31	2.69	10.20	50.56	22.64	17.64	29.31	5.11
	± SE	0.55	1.97	0.72	4.02	0.07	1.05	2.47	0.08	0.26	0.19	2.81	0.52	1.36	1.38	0.22
III	Mean	8.46	80.22	131.75	31.75	3.38	14.31	120.81	1.35	3.01	10.92	51.51	22.27	19.30	28.16	5.34
	± SE	0.73	1.67	1.05	2.01	0.07	1.50	4.48	0.04	0.35	0.80	1.10	0.79	1.55	1.62	0.33
IV	Mean	9.22	81.68	132.02	35.88	3.41	15.29	129.30	1.32	2.63	10.93	50.18	21.60	23.30	23.77	5.47
	± SE	0.57	0.94	1.12	1.94	0.17	0.64	4.92	0.10	0.16	0.68	1.80	0.39	2.28	2.17	0.61
V	Mean	8.38	79.88	133.22	34.51	3.57	16.62	134.85	1.46	2.82	11.89	51.52	21.94	22.80	25.88	5.83
	± SE	0.64	2.10	0.94	1.63	0.16	0.74	5.31	0.09	0.31	0.60	1.53	0.71	1.26	1.47	0.47

Table 7.2 . Clusters means for fifteen characters in lentil over three late environments

Cluster		Days to Germination	Days to 50% Flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	No of pri. branches/plant	No of sec. branches/plant	No of Pods/plant	No of seeds/pod	100- seed weight (g)	No of nodes upto first flower	No of Fruiting nodes/plant	Protein content	Biological Yield (g/plant)	Harvest index (%)	Seed yield (g/plant)
I	Mean	8.46	76.76	128.95	29.04	3.18	14.87	124.38	1.39	2.58	10.92	48.32	22.83	20.82	25.97	5.23
	± SE	0.18	2.02	1.03	5.02	0.11	0.89	6.35	0.08	0.19	0.78	1.15	0.56	1.95	2.33	0.16
II	Mean	9.02	81.11	129.93	33.67	3.25	12.80	120.98	1.34	2.70	10.78	50.10	22.29	17.68	28.01	4.88
	± SE	0.43	1.81	0.70	3.26	0.11	0.96	2.59	0.02	0.29	0.33	0.95	0.61	1.02	2.19	0.36
III	Mean	8.00	79.24	129.28	31.08	3.16	14.33	121.65	1.31	2.89	10.71	52.23	22.16	17.84	29.98	5.26
	± SE	0.40	1.69	0.37	2.39	0.08	1.44	3.99	0.05	0.26	0.80	1.34	0.63	1.69	2.10	0.23
IV	Mean	8.54	80.60	130.36	33.41	3.23	15.57	132.52	1.48	2.64	12.05	50.59	21.62	22.65	26.23	5.82
	± SE	0.47	2.09	1.14	0.99	0.16	1.60	4.41	0.04	0.21	0.71	1.32	0.31	1.37	2.03	0.15
V	Mean	8.36	78.69	132.25	33.42	3.51	15.05	129.40	1.37	2.86	10.98	53.63	22.07	21.61	27.13	5.66
	± SE	0.43	1.19	1.04	1.92	0.20	1.09	8.54	0.04	0.29	0.82	0.90	0.93	1.24	1.48	0.32

Table 8.1 . Estimates of average intra and inter- cluster distances for five clusters in lentil over three normal environments

Clusters	I	II	III	IV	
I	2.975				
II	6.041	2.401			
III	4.585	3.742	2.768		
IV	5.270	4.384	3.448	2.782	
V	4.904	5.478	3.811	3.215	2.861

Table 8.2 . Estimates of average intra and inter- cluster distances for five clusters in lentil over three late environments

Clusters	I	II	III	IV	
I	2.933				
II	3.802	2.488			
III	3.728	3.239	2.628		
IV	4.144	4.818	4.799	2.691	
V	4.839	4.660	4.173	3.640	2.874

Table 9.1 . Clustering pattern of twenty nine lentil genotypes on basis of Non-hierarchical Euclidean Cluster analysis for fifteen characters over three normal environments

Clusters	No of genotypes	Genotypes
I	3	19 20 23
II	3	5 8 9
III	8	1 4 7 11 12 13 14 24
IV	6	2 17 18 21 22 27
V	9	3 6 10 15 16 25 26 28 29

Table 9.2 . Clustering pattern of twenty nine lentil genotypes on basis of Non-hierarchical Euclidean Cluster analysis for fifteen characters over three late environments

Clusters	No of genotypes	Genotypes
I	6	18 19 20 23 24 28
II	5	4 5 8 9 22
III	6	1 7 11 12 13 14
IV	8	2 3 6 17 21 26 27 29
V	4	10 15 16 25

Conclusion

The study revealed the presence of substantial genetic variability among lentil genotypes evaluated under normal and late sown conditions. Traits such as number of pods per plant, biological yield per plant, harvest index and 100-seed weight were identified as key contributors to seed yield. High heritability coupled with high genetic advance for these traits indicates good scope for improvement through selection. Genetic divergence analysis identified diverse genotypes that can be exploited as parents in breeding programmes aimed at developing high yielding and widely adaptable lentil varieties.

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